

Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) Approach: Importance in Speaking Skills

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Abstract:

Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) is a way to deal with the education of second and unknown dialects, emphasizing cooperation as both the method and the last objective of learning a language. The targets are (1) to discover the Effectiveness of the CLT Approach in Improving Speaking Ability. (2) huge contrasts between students instructed by CLT and those not. Quantitative research is an actual design experiment. The design used was a pretest-posttest control group design. The population is the students who are learning the English language. The research uses cluster random sampling with two group designs (experiment group and control group). Data was broken down using a t-test, and the t-test score was 2.744. A score of the t-table is at a 5% level of importance, and on a level of 62, it is 1.670; the t-test result is higher than the t-table ($2.744 > 1.670$). The T-test hypothesis is rejected, and the T-table hypothesis is accepted. CLT improves speaking capability.

Keywords: CLT, Speaking

Introduction:

Teaching and learning English comprises four aptitudes. They are writing, speaking, reading, and listening. As of late, speaking has assumed an inexorably vital job in second and unknown dialect

settings as a day-to-day correspondence method. Speaking is either gainful or dynamic expertise. Even though those four abilities are similarly vital, speaking becomes the most critical device to impart that should be cultivated. Speaking is one of the English abilities that is an incredible job used to associate among individuals worldwide. Talking is one of the sorts of forming in language, which is quick, confounded, continuous, and essential because the language itself is an image to use by communicators to develop and pass on data.

The curriculum has permanently changed in the history of the education system. As Sauvignon (1987) mentioned, an end goal is to speak to the emotional, physical, and psychological features of second-language learning and to describe the different sorts of exercises that have their place in the present informative educational program. Furthermore, it was further stated by (1987) that the parity of highlights will and ought to differ starting with one educational program and then onto the next, contingent upon the specific setting of which it is a section, where informative skill is objective. This curriculum focuses on student-centered learning, where students must be more active than their teacher.

The teacher only explains the material and asks the students to answer the question in the book without knowing whether the students have understood. In this case, the students will be passive. The students think speaking is tedious, whereas they just read and answer the questions. Even though the students have learned to speak from elementary to junior high school, they still need help speaking. Some things students could improve:

- They feel afraid to speak in English.
- They need help finding the vocabulary.
- They need help understanding unfamiliar words.
- They are not used to speaking English every day and need more motivation.

To solve the problems of speaking above, the teacher needs to use a suitable approach.

There are plenty of methods for instructing speaking. One of them is utilizing Communication Language Teaching. That turns into the famous way to deal with being connected. The fundamental

procedure of Communication Language Teaching (CLT) is having the understudies utilize the objective language to do an inventive errand, for example, role-playing, dramas, or songs, to achieve the open objective of the educational programs. Moreover, open language exercises as amusements not simply cultivate the students' enthusiasm for a fun route in their learning procedure but can be utilized to learn new things and practice language structures to help the students' aficionado of language improvement. Also, they will be increasingly specific and be progressively persuaded to take a speaking class.

CLT extensively applies the hypothetical viewpoint of the Communication Approach by making open capability the objective of language education and recognizing the relationship between communication and language. What this looks like in the classroom may rely upon how the fundamentals are translated and connected (Widdowson: 1990). Also, explain further the importance of CLT supposedly not as a British, European, or U.S. wonder, but instead, a global exertion to react to the requirements of present-day language students in a wide range of learning settings (Barnard et al., 2008).

They teach each of the four aptitudes: writing, speaking, reading, and listening. It becomes obligatory for English educators to control the understudies to accomplish those capacities by showing them as fascinating as could reasonably be expected. In this manner, talking is an unquestionable requirement to be shown different abilities. The extended, intelligent perspective on language conduct they offer exhibits various difficulties for instructors (Barnard et al., 2008)

Instructing English as an unknown dialect in middle school is troublesome. Be that as it may, the teacher must create a great system to encourage students to learn English. Byrne in Syafaruddin (2001) expressed that the educator who trains an unknown dialect sets the student into a circumstance where the students effectively take an interest as an individual from the social network. As explained further, CLT emphasizes the student. Student information needs to give a structure to explain program objectives regarding utilitarian ability (Barnard et al., 2008). This means the teacher should create suitable techniques for the topic. So the students feel happy, comfortable, and

motivated in the teaching and learning process. Moreover, it makes them more active while learning English in the classroom.

Teaching activities in the classroom are aimed at achieving individual language use. This needs teachers not only to create a warm and humanistic classroom atmosphere but also to create an active speaker. Teachers are also the most influential factors that determine the success of students' speaking abilities, and teachers are also the most influential people in classroom speaking activities. English teachers usually transfer the language by using appropriate methods, techniques, media, evaluation, classroom activities, etc. Brown and Alfira (1998) stated that the teaching of speaking is to give aptitude for speaking: fluency and communication. The interaction is focused on the idea of general correspondence. Along these lines, the instructor should support the students by taking them to a real-life situation so they can use English fluency and accuracy. Teaching English to junior high school students is a big challenge for teachers, especially in speaking. Students expect to be able to communicate fluently in English. It is not only the ability to get the speaker's information but also to produce good pronunciation. The teachers expect their students to speak English very well.

In fact, in teaching speaking at junior high school, it is difficult for teachers and students to implement speaking. Many teachers need help finding good techniques for teaching speaking, and students find it difficult to express their ideas. Hence, the writer uses video to improve students' speaking ability to describe pets. Teaching speaking in Junior High School is more complex work. Most of the students need help with pronunciation. The teacher should work hard to solve their problems. The teacher should know how to motivate the students in speaking activities. This can be done by selecting an excellent and exciting approach. In this case, the Communication Language Teaching (CLT) approach is one of the excellent and exciting approaches to be applied. Key to a comprehension of informative language instructing is a comprehension of the term open ability (Savignon, 1987)

The issue of encouraging speaking is mind-boggling. It still needs to be identified with the understudies' factor in addition to

setting outside. From the inner angles, the issues are identified with the local language, age, presentation, intrinsic phonetic capacity, character and language sense of self, and inspiration and worry for good talking. The purposes of those issues are identified with the state of the students.

In the outer issue, encouraging speaking has a challenge to make appropriate study hall hours because, for the most part, in the lesser or senior secondary school, English exercises just four hours every week, so they constrain time. They do not augment their capacity to polish; they do not have the maximum time to rehearse outside of the homeroom because the instructor should show reasonableness with the schedule from the administration, recollecting that there is a last examination from the legislature. They do not have room schedule-wise to rehearse outside the classroom since they do not have a reasonable accomplice to talk in English, and in reality, they 'talk in their local language.

Based on the problems above, it suggests that the teacher chooses a suitable method based on the problems they find in their teaching. The writer takes research to the eighth graders. In light of the schedule of educational modules 2013, in the second semester, students learn role-playing and dramas. The writer teaches both because it is appropriate for the research reading strategy. Speaking is a beneficial aptitude. This is a movement of delivering words or sentences orally. With that expertise, individuals contemplate their thoughts and contemplate the world. Through talking, individuals have a simple method to speak with others legitimately or by implication. It resembles what Brown and Yale (89: 14) express: talking expresses the need to demand data, administration, etc.

There are many definitions of speaking. Syafrudin (2001) indicates that talking is a beneficial aptitude for oral correspondence. Finocchiaro and Bonomo in Syafaruddin(2001) expressed that talking is like at least one sound made by the person for correspondence. Near, Chaney in Alfira (1998) says that talking is the route toward structure and sharing significance. Along these lines, the understudy should be able to educate their thoughts concerning a few issues or things. The goal of talking is to improve understudies' enlightening capacity. The

understudies can improve their talking limits and add to their convictions by expressing their considerations.

Donough and Shaw (1993) state that talking is the approach to expressing thoughts and supposition, communicating and wanting to accomplish something, arranging or taking care of a specific issue, and keeping up social relationships and fellowship. Long and Richard (1982) say talking is an intricate arrangement of capacity that includes numerous parts, including elocutions, listening, and language structure aptitude. Nolascco and Arthur (1987) state that speaking is a conversation or interaction. Finochiro and Bonomo (1987) stated that speaking combines several skills. Moreover, there are six points to be done by the learner:

1. Describing what he wants to say
2. Choosing the pattern
3. Choosing the worlds that fit the meaning
4. Using correct arranges of sounds
5. Making sure what he wants to say is inappropriate situation
6. Placing his tongue and lips in a good position

Mackey (in Magiono, 2007:13) characterizes talking as an oral articulation that includes suitable examples of beat and sound and the correct request to pass on the correct significance. Chaney (1998:13) contends that talking is the way toward structure and sharing significance using verbal and non-verbal images in various settings. That language is first spoken. It implies that talking is the essential ability and the most critical expertise of language, like the announcement referenced by Tupan (1995:14). Also, Harmer (2007) states that talking is expertise that turns into a vital piece of day-by-day life; it is the line for individuals to make a social relationship as a person, so it should be created and practice autonomously in the language structure educational programs.

From the above definition, it very well may be clear that talking is communicating thoughts, sentiments, or emotions to others by utilizing words or hints of enunciation to educate, convince, and engage that can be learned by utilizing some instructing learning strategies.

The teaching of speaking has a few standards, such as Nunan

(2003: 54-56) (1): Be mindful of the contrasts between second language and unknown dialect learning settings. (An unknown dialect setting is one where the objective language is not the language of correspondence in the general public, and after that, a second language setting is one where the objective language is the language of correspondence in the general public), (2) Give students practice with both familiarity and precision. (Precision is how much students' talk matches what people honestly state when they use the goal language, and nature is how much speakers use the language quickly and, with a couple of waverings of unnatural delays, false begins, and word seeks). (3) Provide open doors for understudies to talk by utilizing bunch work or pair work and restricting instructor talk; (4) Plan to talk errands that include an exchange/for importance. The exploration suggests that understudies progress by bestowing in the target language since correspondence incorporates endeavoring to grasp and make you understood. (5) Design study hall exercises with direction and practice in value-based and speaking collaboration.

Talking is an intelligent procedure of developing implying that includes creating, getting, and handling data. It is also defined as the capability to pronounce articulation and vocabulary to express, state, and convey thought, idea, and feeling. While the way toward educating and learning a language is by speaking, students receive information from others through their conversations, after which they should understand the information, communicate their understanding, and respond to it. As indicated by Brown (2004) in Kusumawardani (2013:9) In Dian Rahmatika (2015:29), there are five essential kinds of talking, as pursues: (1) Imitative, A continuum of sorts of talking execution is the capacity just to parrot back or emulate a word, expression, statement or even sentence which speaker got notification from the other speaker. Imitative evaluations could be planned by unit, helping to start understudies learning fundamental themed vocabulary.

This is a case of talking material that understudies can present with the instructor's assistance and perform for the class. (2) Intensive, The creation of short stretches of oral language intended to show ability in a restricted band of linguistic, express, lexical, or phonological relationship (for example, prosodic components – sound

– stress – beat – crossroads), (3) Responsive, The errands incorporate connection just as test cognizance which is usually done between two individuals. It tends to be done at the restricted dimension of short discussions, standard welcome, casual discussion, solicitation, remarks, or the structure collaboration like a meeting, television show, etc. (4) Interactive: The refinement among responsive and canny talking is in the length and complexity of the affiliation. It here and there incorporates various trades or potentially different members; (5) Extensive (monolog), Extensive oral generation assignments incorporate discourses, oral introductions, and narrating, amid which the open door for oral communication from crowd individuals are either significantly compelled (possibly to nonverbal responses) or limited all around.

The English teacher needs to understand those five speaking types, which involve imitative, intensive, responsive, interactive, and extensive. The latest one, extensive speaking, is employed in this research, where the students are assigned to have oral presentations and deliver a speech. Not to mention responsive speaking is also used because, on one occasion, the writer gets the students to have a conversation by doing role play. In addition, competence in speaking includes the ability to use appropriate speech for the circumstances and when deviating from the normal to convey.

Impact Of Clt On Speaking Skills:

Brown (2001) states that a few things, for example, Elocution, vocabulary, familiarity, highlight, and punctuation, ought to be used to have the capacity to talk well. As a mind-boggling action, talking has vital perspectives in the accompanying (1) Accuracy; accuracy in talking is using the correct type of syntax, vocabulary, and Elocution. Those three sections include making an exact expression, Sparrt, and companions (2005:34). Elocution is essential to language adapting, particularly in the talking capacity. Harmer (2007) states that education is not just barely making the understudies separate sounds and sound highlights but also can improve their talking capacity endlessly, for instance, by centering around sounds and making understudies aware of using weight while conveying sound.

Vocabulary is the foundation of a language. In other words,

students with good speaking ability must master vocabulary. Harmer (2007) says that if the understudies have more vocabulary or, if nothing else, 1000 words, they can impart them quickly. They only set aside a short effort to express what they will state since they comprehend what words can depict their thoughts. Familiarity is critical in talking precision. If our discourse is overflowing with semantic slip-ups, your musings will not get transversely finished so successfully. Those three sections are imperative components to achieve the exactness in the exertion of having the capacity to talk well, (2) Fluency, Fluency expressed by Sparrt and companions (2005:34) is talking at a typical speed decisively, redundancy, and with smooth utilization of associated discourse. It manages how agreeable understudies are, the point at which they talk, and how effectively the words turn out, regardless of whether there are extraordinary delays and holes in the understudy is talking. It is a parameter of the understudy's talking capacity objective. (3) Accent: the accents of one speaker and others differ. This is because everyone has their particular manner of saying words, depending upon the speaker's way of life.

Brown (2001) claims that instructional systems in CLT must engage understudies to partake in open joint efforts with each other. Here comes the centrality of building up the idea of articulation and arrangement of significance, as supported by Sauvignon (1991; 1997). CLT like this requires joining language use for monumental purposes in unrehearsed settings, that is, the earnest, genuine, and utilitarian usage of language into valuable errands. Significant to this thought, Lee and VanPatten (1995) guarantee that phonetic contribution to which students should go ought to be essential and understandable. Students can express, translate, and consult through cooperation in informative occasions containing significant, bona fide, practical, and conceivable etymological info.

The last normal for classrooms of CLT, as proposed by Brown (2001), is that the job of students is focal since they are offered chances to create self-governing learning dependent on their learning styles and methodologies, while the job of educators is fringe, that will be, that of facilitator and guide of students' exercises. The possibility

of student-centeredness has additionally been recognized by Sauvignon (2003), who proposes that CLT focuses on students regarding procedures and objectives. The attention on students as far as procedure alludes to a similar idea of learning self-governance as proposed by Brown (2001), while the emphasis on students in association with objectives implies that students' informative needs should fill in as a system for explaining and distinguishing program targets. The last normal for classrooms of CLT, as proposed by Brown (2001), is that the job of students is focal since they are offered chances to create self-governing learning dependent on their learning styles and methodologies, while the job of educators is fringe, that will be, that of facilitator and guide of students' exercises. The possibility of student-centeredness has additionally been recognized by Sauvignon (2003), who proposes that CLT focuses on students regarding procedures and objectives. The attention on students as far as procedure alludes to a similar idea of learning self-governance as proposed by Brown (2001), while the emphasis on students in association with objectives implies that students' informative needs should fill in as a system for explaining and distinguishing program targets. The procedure of the Communication Language Teaching (CLT) Approach is as follows: (1) Presentation of a brief dialog or several mini-dialogs, (2) Oral practice of each utterance of the dialog segment to be presented that day, (3) Question and answer based on the dialog topic, (4) Question and answer related to the student's personal experience, (5) Study one of the essential communicative expression in dialog, (6) Learner discovery of generalizations or rules underlying the functional expression, (7) Oral recognition, interpretative activities, (8) Oral production activities proceeding from guided to more accessible communication activities, (9) Duplicating of the exchange or modules on the off chance that they are not in the class content, (10) Sampling of the composed homework task, (11) Evaluation of learning.

There are some advantages of CLT: (1) The interaction between students and teachers: Communicative teaching is becoming an increasingly clear feature in the change in how the internship students build up the subject and activity and become progressively

imperative. Instructor-student relationship is an intuitive, agreeable relationship, as opposed to the conventional training, the sort of ace hireling relationship, (2) To illuminate the fundamental learning and capacity to skillfully consolidate the advancement: Traditional study hall educating of English in the primary body of the cost of the home examination, just stressed the educators on the information of the methodical and trustworthiness, which is an instructor focused, knowledge-centered from the medieval "scholastic" teaching methods inherited One consequence of the neglect of student ability. Communicative teaching emphasizes the learner's cognitive ability and operational capabilities, which allow the students to think about and express their views, thus training the ability to use language to communicate in real life. (3) This technique increases the teacher-student relationship. It is an interactive relationship. (4) Communication Language Teaching (CLT) allows students to recognize and exhibit their abilities. In this way, the students can enjoy learning the target language.

The specific detriments of CLT are as follows: (1) It is felt that there needs to be more accentuation on the rectification of articulation and language structure blunder. It is because of an over-the-top measure of focus on the significance of the inconvenience of structure, (2) the CLT approach bases on commonality yet not precision in language structure and verbalization, (3) The CLT approach is unimaginable for widely appealing understudy and pushed understudies, yet for Beginners some controlled practice is required, (4) The watching limit of the instructor must be astoundingly incredible, (5) Grammar Teaching Practices utilize this strategy troublesome, (6) CLT approach centers around familiarity yet not exactness in sentence structure and articulation, (7) The CLT approach is extraordinary for middle of the road understudy and propelled understudies, yet for Beginners some controlled practice is required, (8) The checking capacity of the educator must be excellent Grammar Teaching Practices make utilization of this methodology troublesome. Speaking is either a profitable or dynamic ability. Even though those four abilities are similarly vital, talking becomes the most vital instrument to convey that should be practiced. Speaking is one of the

English aptitudes, and it is an extraordinary job used to socialize among people worldwide. Speaking is one of the sorts of forming in language. This sort is quick, convoluted, continuous, and essential because the language itself is an image to use by communicators to build and pass on data. Tarigan (1990:3-4) portrays that speaking is a language capacity made in adolescent life, conveyed by listening mastery, and at that period, talking skills are discovered.

Given Competence, Curriculum talking is one of the four essential capabilities the understudies should increase well. It has a vital job in correspondence. Talking can be discovered in the spoken cycle, particularly in the Joint Construction of Text (Department et al., 2004). In finishing talking, understudies face a couple of difficulties, one of them is about language itself. Most understudies have trouble talking even though they have plenty of vocabulary and have kept in touch with them well. The issues are uneasy for understudies to submit mistakes.

Speaking is a beneficial aptitude. It could not be isolated from tuning in. When we talk, we produce the substance, which should be vital. In the possibility of correspondence, we can find the speaker, the group of onlookers, the message, and the info. Talking could not be isolated from Elocution as it urges students to learn English sounds. Harmer (in Tarigan, 1990: 12) states that when appearing or conveying ability, we can apply three imperative stages: (1) introducing a new dialect, (2) practicing, and (3) Communicating.

The expression "Communication Language Teaching" (CLT) implies distinctive things to various instructors. To specific instructors, it implies a more prominent accentuation on using objective language in the study hall, specifically, a more prominent accentuation on ethical quality. To various teachers, the correspondence includes exchanging dark information between examiners. Finally, a couple of teachers understand correspondence most around the world in anthropological terms, that is, as a social bond structure for making meaning. Even with the diverse implications of CLT, all the module instructors advocate for an open technique. Communication Language Teaching (CLT) has become a well-known way to deal with being connected. The fundamental

method of Communication Language Teaching (CLT) has the understudies utilize objective language to complete an imaginative errand; for example, diversions show melodies or pretend to accomplish the open objective of the educational programs.

Method:

This examination utilized quantitative methodology. Quantitative methodology involves collecting data and analyzing it numerically using statistical techniques. All subjects are measured using this approach, but only the experimental group receives treatment. To check the improvement of the real ding achi basement, a posttest was applied to discover the students' speaking capacity after they were instructed to use communication language teaching (CLT). According to Khotari (2004:5), a quantitative approach can be further sub-classified into experimental, inferential, and simulation approaches.

This research is experimental. This research used a proper experimental design. Actual experimental design can be classified into two kinds. Experimental design is used in this research. This research used the Posttest Control Group Design. In this design, two groups were taken using the sampling technique. One group is the experimental group (with treatment), and another is the control group (without treatment). Subjects are partitioned into two: control group and experimental group. The instrument is checked in first by giving an out to the students in a different group. After the instrument is valid and reliable, the writer tests it on both groups as a pre-test. After that pretreatment, the treatment is given to the experimental group. A group of experimental students is educated by utilizing communication language teaching. The group of control is educated about speaking traditionally. Both groups had the same materials. The posttest is carried out after the process of pretreatment and also treatment.

Margono (2004:118) says that the population is all the data concerning us in the scope and time we specify. The number of populations in this research is eighth graders of SMP N 1 Tegal in the scholarly year 2018/2019. The number of eighth graders is 268, divided into nine classes. Margono (2004:121) says that the sample is

part of the population. Based on the population, there are two classes (8F and 8I) as a research sample. The sample was broken down into two groups. The first group consists of 32 students, and it is an experimental group. The second is 32 students as a control group. Research utilizes the technique of random sampling to get samples. In the technique of taking the sample from the population to get a representative sample, every subject of the population has the same opportunity to become a member of the sample.

In this technique of taking the sample from the population to get a representative sample, every subject of the population has the same opportunity to become a member of the sample. Research utilizes the technique of random sampling to get samples. Researchers explained that the simple meaning of a variable could be defined as the characteristic of an individual, object, indication, or event, which is measured quantitatively and qualitatively. Variables in this research are (1) The independent variable is Communication language Teaching, and (2) The dependent is students' speaking capacity.

They state that the data-collecting technique is how we collect data, such as the data-collecting technique in questionnaires, Interviews, and observations. They state that there are some data collection techniques: (1) Observation and (2) Data Collecting Techniques in Tests. This research uses the "test" technique to know how CLT affects students' Speaking capability. Data was collected by using several steps: (1) Giving a treatment to the experiment and control group using Communication Language Teaching (CLT), (2) Giving a test to the control and experiPurposeoup; the purpose of a given test is to discover the effect on students' speaking ability after using Communication Language Teaching (CLT) Approach. The data was collected through tests used as a parameter of the research. The test was given to other students who did not belong to the experimental and control groups to prove the validity and reliability of the research instruments.

A *legitimate instrument test* is the point at which it can quantify what ought to be estimated. A test has legitimacy if it connects the test results and the criteria. Before the test was carried out on control and experimental groups, it was tested on other students

who did not belong to those groups to determine its validity. The research used validity of internal know the test validity. It is a trying test out to 32 students at seventh-grade students.

Data are analyzed using several tests to measure mean, median, modus, standard deviation, variant, and t-test. According to researchers, either one of the ways to examine two averages is used, such as a t-test.

Results And Discussion:

This research was conducted in six activities. The five activities were teaching-learning activities. The writer used the actual experimental design posttest only. There are 64 students as a sample. The first class consists of 32 students as an experimental and the second group of 32 students for the control group. The results of the posttest of the control group showed that the average achievement of the students' posttest was 66.4. Based on the students' speaking ability, the score was considered fair and did not pass the passing grade. The researcher concluded that the students still experienced issues to communicate in English. For the deviation standard, the result is 14.44.

The consequence of the posttest of The Experiment Group was that the average achievement of the students' posttest was 75.7. Based on the student's achievement table, the score is considered a 'good' level and passed the passing grade. The students' talking capacity by utilizing Communication Language Teaching (CLT) significantly differed. For calculating deviation, the standard is 4.41. The variant test result is 19.36. As suggested by Best (1981), for subjects that require fixed calculation, for example, science and material science, the 1 percent (0.1) alpha dimension of hugeness can be utilized. Since this proposition managed the instructive circle, the 5 percent (0.5) alpha dimension of essentialness was used for the mental and instructive cycles.

The experiment has 32 students for the group experiment and 32 for the control group. Along these lines, the number of students in the two groups was 64. Freedom of degree (pdf) was 32, acquired from the formula $N_e + N_c - 2 = 62$. The primary incentive with the df 62 at a 5 percent alpha dimension of significance is 1.670. The acquired t value

is 2.744, so the t value is higher than the fundamental value ($2.744 > 1.670$). It is concluded that there was significant use of Communication Language Teaching. Implementing the Communication Language Teaching Strategy in instructing the SMP N 1 Tegal eighth graders was conducted in 6 meetings involving treatment and posttest. The treatment consisted of 5 meetings, and students got many kinds of dialog text. The posttest consisted of 1 meeting. Researchers found that participants in a group of experiments looked excited about the communication language teaching method for teaching speaking.

The primary incentive with the df 62 at 5 percent alpha dimension of criticalness is 1,670. The acquired t value is 2.744, so the t value is higher than the fundamental value ($2.744 > 1.670$). It is concluded that there was significant use of Communication Language Teaching. This method also demonstrates that the student's scores in the group of the experiment are superior to the student's scores in the group of control.

Conclusion:

From the result analysis, the score of the t-test is 2.744. The score of the t-table is at a 5% level of significance, and the degree of 62 is 1.670. Thus, the t-table is lower than the t-test ($2.744 > 1.670$). According to the data result, the t-test hypothesis is presumed to be rejected, and the t-table hypothesis is acknowledged. That means there is a positive effect to improving students' speaking ability between students who are educated by utilizing Communication Language Teaching (CLT) and individuals who are not educated by utilizing Communication Language Teaching (CLT). The difference between the t-test and t-table means a lot in determining the effectiveness of CLT implementation. According to the analysis, Communication Language Teaching (CLT) positively improves speaking ability.

Teaching English to junior high school students is a big challenge for teachers, especially in speaking. Students expect to be able to speak English fluently. Teaching speaking requires an appropriate strategy that focuses on not only linguistic competence but also communicative competence. Communication Language Teaching (CLT), which empowers students to develop their soft and

hard skills, is recommended for teaching, particularly in speaking. During the time spent educating and learning a language, the ability to speak enables students to accept information from others through their conversation, after which they should understand the information, communicate their understanding, and respond to it. CLT is recommended for use in all levels of English learning. Teachers should respond positively in implementing related approaches to get the most effective way of teaching speaking.

References:

- Arikunto, Suharsimi. 2006. *Prosedur Penelitian Suatu Pendekatan Praktik*. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.
- Arikunto, Suharsimi. 2010. *Prosedur Penelitian*. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.
- Barnard, R., Richards, J. C., & Rodgers, T. S. (2008). *Approaches and Methods in Language Teaching*. TESOL Quarterly. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3588247>
- Brown H. Douglas. 2001. *Teaching by Principles: An Interactive Approach to Language Pedagogy*. San Francisco: San Francisco University.
- Brown H. Douglas. 2003. *Language Assessments: Principal and Classroom Practices*, New York: Pearson Education, Ltd.
- Chaney, A.L., T.L. Burke, *Teaching oral communication in Grades K 8*. Boston: Allyn and Bacon, 1998. *Journal of Engineering Technology and Education*, Vol. 7, No.1 March 2010, pp.126142.
- Harmer, J. 2001. *The Practice of English Language Teaching* (3rd Ed.). London and New York: Longman Group.
- Khotari, C.R. 2004. *Research Methodology*. New Delhi: New Age International (P) Ltd.
- Magiono. 2007. *Improving the Students' Speaking Skills through Debate in the Third Year of Accounting 2 of SMKN 1*

Banyuwangi. Graduate Thesis, unpublished, Malang. The Islamic University of Malang. Graduate Program in English Language Education.

Rahmatika, Dian. 2015. The Effect of Implementing Project-Based Learning Strategy on Students' Speaking Ability. Tegal: Pancasakti University.

Sudjana, Nana. (2009). Tuntunan Penyusunan Karya Ilmiah. Cetakan Keduabelas. Bandung. Sinar Baru Algensindo

Savignon, S. J. (1987). Communicative Language Teaching. Theory Into Practice. <https://doi.org/10.1080/004058470>